

the radio halo lights up and the cluster migrates up to the correlation. After ~ 1 Gyr, the cluster appears dynamically relaxed again, the radio emission fades away and the cluster goes back to the upper limits region. In agreement with this picture, we found a trend between the distance from the correlation and the dynamical disturbance of galaxy clusters, i.e. more powerful radio halos are found in the most disturbed clusters (Figure 1, bottom panel).

- This sample allowed us to show for the first time that the fraction of radio halos drops in low mass systems, in agreement with the turbulent acceleration model (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Expected fraction of cluster with radio halos as a function of the cluster mass with cutoff frequency 600 MHz (red line and shadowed region) and 140 MHz (blue line and shadowed region). The black lines represent the observed fraction of radio halos in two mass bins: the low mass ($M_{500} < 8 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$) and the high mass bin ($M_{500} > 8 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$). Figure adapted from [10].

The statistical studies of radio halos have remained limited so far to massive clusters ($M_{500} > 5 - 6 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$) and high observational frequencies. This does not allow us to test the most important prediction of models, i.e. the existence of a population of USSRHs only detectable at low frequency and the consequent increase of the fraction of halos that should be seen in samples observed at low frequencies.

The LOFAR revolution

In order to overcome the current limits and be able to test the most important expectation of the turbulent re-

acceleration model, sensitive low frequency observations are necessary. To date, the Low Frequency Array (LOFAR, [12]) is the best instrument to perform such a test. The main reasons are the high sensitivity to the extended emission, combined with the high resolution, needed to disentangle the contribution of discrete sources blended with radio halos. Not only LOFAR is allowing the exploration of a new frequency window (10-240 MHz), but it is also allowing us to probe new cluster mass ranges (down to $M_{500} > 1 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$), where the majority of USSRHs should be found.

Using the data from the LOFAR Two Meter Sky Survey (LoTSS, [13]) we are carrying out the first systematic study of radio halos at 150 MHz. Specifically, we analysed the radio images of all the 309 Planck clusters [11] within the LoTSS data release 2 (Shimwell et al. in prep.) in order to search for diffuse emission. These clusters span a large redshift ($z = 0.016 - 0.9$) and the mass range ($M_{500} = 1 - 12 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$). We identified ~ 80 radio halos (Botteon et al., in prep.). This is the largest sample of galaxy clusters observed at low frequency and the largest sample of radio halos analysed so far. The statistical exploitation of these data is ongoing (Cuciti et al., in prep., Cassano et al., in prep.). This unique sample will allow us to 1) extend previous studies to lower mass ranges and higher redshift, where we expect to find the majority of USSRHs; 2) measure the occurrence of radio halos at low frequency and compare it with the results obtained at high frequency; 3) study the radio power – mass correlation at low frequency and down to low masses. This work, combined with higher frequency (GMRT and VLA) follow ups that are already ongoing will allow us to perform the first statistically solid study of the spectral behaviour of radio halos, providing the missing and crucial test for current models, together with new constraints for the development of future more sophisticated models and simulations.

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Short CV

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